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geostudiesjournal@gmail.com

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Address:	Department of Geography & Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Science, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.
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SMALLHOLDER FARMERS' ACCESS TO CLIMATE CHANGE INFORMATION IN THE NIGER DELTA

Prof. Onovughe Ikelegbe and Dr Joshua Longe
Department of Sociology and Anthropology,
Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Benin, Benin City
Author's E-mail: Joshua.longe@uniben.edu

Abstract: *The study examined the essentiality of the availability and access of climate information services (CIS) to root crop farmers in Niger Delta, Nigeria. The sample population consisted of four hundred (400) farmers from the three ecological regions of Delta State. Field surveys were conducted with the aid of questionnaire and local language translators. Data were presented in simple percentages. CIS channels available are both formal and informal. Results showed that CIS is highly unavailable in the study area. Root crop farmers lack adequate access to climate information and largely rely on indigenous knowledge in their farming activities. The study suggests government involvement in terms of upscaling the capacity of agricultural officers, providing farmers more access to internet and mobile applications, awareness campaigns, capacity-building initiatives and co-production of local-specific CIS. This should be accompanied by agrometeorological advisories to overcome these barriers to the access and use of CIS.*

Keywords – Smallholder farmers, Agriculture, climate Information, Access, Availability.

INTRODUCTION

The accessibility and wider use of climate information services (CIS) are essential to enable farmers to minimize losses due to climatic uncertainties and take advantage of opportunities presented by favourable climatic conditions (Onyeneke et al., 2023; Alidu et al., 2022; Shikwambana and Malaza, 2022). This is expected to improve agricultural production and build climate-resilience in the most vulnerable smallholder farming, particularly under rainfed farming systems (Myeni, 2024). He notes that, despite significant efforts in research on the development and dissemination of CIS, the accessibility and utilization of such information by smallholder farmers is still low and unsatisfactory in Africa. In consequence, most African smallholder farmers continue to solely rely on indigenous knowledge of local agroecological experience to predict weather patterns and make weather-sensitive decisions that are crucial for their agricultural production (Ogundeji et al., 2022; Baffour et al., 2022).

However, the indigenous knowledge acquired over years of farming experience has become unreliable and insufficient to cope with the current climate variability and change which is beyond their experience scope and traditional coping mechanisms (Ogundeji et al., 2022). Most smallholder farmers are not using any CIS in planning their farm activities due to unreliability, lack of tailored and local-specific CIS (farm or community level) as well as language barriers, difficulty in understanding, decoding and use of supplied information for decision-making (Myeni, 2024).

The present occurrence of climate change being experienced globally, Nigeria inclusive, has emphasized the importance of climate information services (CIS) in agriculture and root crop farming in particular. Root crop farmers in Nigeria largely rely on rainfed agriculture and indigenous agricultural practices. With the ongoing changes in the weather and climate conditions, the relevance of climate information services to Nigerian farmers

cannot be overemphasized. The availability and access of climate information to smallholder farmers will not only create awareness in their locality but also empower them to grapple with the changes in the weather conditions as well as the shocks and stressors that come with these changes. This will enable them to adopt new farming methods that will enable continued food production that meets the demand for food. The adoption of sustainable climate smart agricultural practices that are more resilient to climate stressors will be of great relevance to indigenous farmers in the Niger Delta.

The value of the CIS information will be in its effective utility by smallholder farmers. Nigerian rural farmers are largely illiterate and may also be rigid in adapting new techniques that will enable smart agriculture. Ruzol et al (2020) argue that by combining traditional knowledge with innovative solutions, rural farmers can optimize crop yields, manage resources more efficiently, while safeguarding their livelihoods against the uncertainties of climate change. This holistic approach ensures that cultural heritage remains respected, while simultaneously equipping farmers with the tools they need to thrive in a changing world. They add that a reliable farm decision model is becoming increasingly important, particularly in countries highly vulnerable to adverse climate change impacts. Nigerian farmers will largely benefit from the development of such a model particularly if it takes cognizance of disparities in the weather conditions of the various ecological regions in their response to climate change.

The Niger Delta is one of the most fragile agroecological zones in Nigeria and vulnerable to the impacts of climate change that in turn impact on the farming practices of root crop farmers. Consequently, the need for a reliable farming decision model is becoming increasingly important. This can only be attained through soliciting information sources which will form the data base on which such a model will be built.

This will help farmers' decision making in their attempt to grapple with the changes in the weather conditions of their localities. Globally, nations have established institutions that will monitor their climate and weather conditions so as to create awareness to all and sundry. Nations include the Phillipines, South Africa, Niger and Nigeria among others. African farmers are largely poor, rigid and illiterate. This makes affordability, accessibility, adaptability and utility of CIS information a major challenge. Basic modes of accessing CIS information is largely through the radio, television, phones etcetera. Accessibility becomes a challenge due to illiteracy, the dearth of extension workers and the inadequate dissemination of CIS information in their local languages.

In the Limpopo region, South Africa, the majority of smallholder farmers had access to the daily weather forecasts that are made available mainly via radio and television while very few had access to other types of CIS such as seasonal weather forecasts and early warnings that are essential to inform agricultural management decisions and strategic plans in advance (Myeni et al, 2024). Furthermore, the majority of smallholder farmers prefer receiving climate and agricultural information that are simplified and translated into their local languages through pre-season workshops or direct voice messages and they were not willing to pay anything for improved and tailored CIS. The majority of smallholder farmers were not using any CIS in planning their farm activities mainly due to unreliability, lack of tailored and local-specific CIS (farm or community level) as well as language barriers, difficulty in understanding, decoding and use of supplied information for decision-making. Information regarding rainfall characteristics, droughts and temperature were the key climate-related information required by smallholder farmers for their decision-making in partitioning land preparation and planting date selection. Sen et. al (2021) argues that the key barriers to

the access and use of climate information by farmers consist of: (1) the lack of farmers' trust of these services; (2) their lack of perceived risk from climate change; and (3) the difficulties in balancing climate adaptation and economic benefits of new interventions.

Despite radio and television being affordable and easy means for conveying CIS, the information obtained from these media sources are generic meteorological forecasts instead of tailored impact-based forecasts coupled with response adaptation strategies that are essential for decision-making (Myeni and Moeletsi, 2020; Agyekum et al., 2022). Furthermore, CIS broadcast via radio and TV follows a top-down approach which confines interaction between CIS developers and the end-users. This prohibits smallholder farmers from understanding and decoding the supplied climate-related information. Therefore, the experts on CIS are encouraged to frequently participate in media interviews at local media stations where they can share insights on the expected weather conditions and advise farmers on local-specific adaptation strategies following an interactive approach and using the local languages (Mandapati, 2018).

The availability, accessibility and utility of this information to smallholder farmers has become a major challenge that needs to be addressed in order to meet the Sustainable Development Goals of meeting zero hunger by 2030. This is essential to enable farmers to minimize losses due to climatic uncertainties. Farmers need to access the relevant information that will enable them carry out climate smart agricultural farm practices that will sustainably produce adequate food to meet the required food demand in Nigeria. The success of this would depend on the effectiveness of the delivery systems available to farmers. Presently, there is a lack of adequate as well as local specific forecasts and advisories where they exist. Nigerian root crop farmers, particularly in the Niger Delta face the

precarity of nature by taking risks with their indigenous farming experiences. This study is also expected to provide crucial information to assist government and other development organizations in developing and implementing effectual policies, programmes and initiatives tailored to advancing the use of CIS by smallholder farmers not only in the study area as well as other regions facing similar challenges especially with an attempt to simplify the complex climate-related information and translate it into local languages.

This study focused on the assessment of smallholder farmers access to climate change information in the Niger Delta, which was achieved through the investigates of ; i) the types of weather and climate information important to farmers; ii) the various modes of climate information sources available to farmers; iii) the frequency by which these information are received ; iv) the barriers to the availability and accessibility of CIS to farmers; as well as v) suggesting how farmers can effectively access and utilize climate information to.

METHODOLOGY

There was an initial reconnaissance survey to the study area to visualise the landscape. This was followed by actual field visits. The three (3) ecological regions of Delta State constituted the sampling frame for the study. A multistage sampling technique was adopted for this study. First, the three ecological zones were mapped out. Second, was the selection of Twenty-five (25%) percent of the nineteen (19) affected Local Government Areas (LGA) from the three (3) ecological zones due to financial constraints. Four (4) communities were selected from each of the five (5) LGAs. Twenty communities were selected in total from which Twenty (20) farmers were selected. A total of four hundred (400) farmers were selected for survey through the use of the snowball sampling technique to identify these farmers. Data relating to the

availability and access of farmers to climate information sources were elicited from structured questionnaires. The results are presented in simple percentages while the frequency of information supply across media types is presented in bar charts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TYPES OF WEATHER AND CLIMATE INFORMATION IMPORTANT TO FARMERS

The basic weather and climate information important to farmers are rainfall and temperature. This is relevant in their planning and decision making in terms of land preparation, on set of planting, fertilizer

application as well as employing available forecasts as a guide to reduce farm losses. Farmers indigenous experience of the weather conditions of their localities constitutes a guide to their farming decisions at all stages.

MODES AND FREQUENCY OF CLIMATE INFORMATION AVAILABLE TO FARMER

The study identified the following mode of making climate information available to farmers in the study area. These include radio, television, bulletins, newspaper, internet, GSM handset, friends, traditional sources, and NiMET (See Table 1).

Table 1: Modes and frequency of supply of Climate information

Media Type	Mode of Communication	Frequency of Supply (per month)
Radio	Audio	12
TV	Audio-Visual	8
Newspapers	Text	4
Mobile Phones	Text/Audio	20
Social Media	Text/Audio-Visual	18
Extension Agents	Face-to-Face	6
Posters/Billboards	Visual/Text	3

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Radio:- Mode of supply of information through radio was largely through pidgin English language 170 (42.5%) and 63 (15.8%) through English language. Other farmers 78 (19.5%) did not respond. This suggests that they may be illiterates or did not have a radio. The frequency of the availability of climate information among farmers through the radio varied as follows; quarterly 100 (25%) bi annually, 80 (20%), annually 25 (6.3%), monthly 38 (9.5%) weekly, 20(5%) and daily 56 (14%).

ii) **Television:-** Mode of supply of information through television was largely through English language 51 (12.8%) pidgin 25 (6.3%), local language 19 (4.8%), no response 305 (76.3%). This suggests

that they may be illiterates or did not have a television set. The frequency of the availability of climate information among farmers through the television varied as follows; quarterly 4 (10%) bi annually, 11 (2.8%), annually 2 (0.5%), monthly 9(2.3%) weekly, 24 (6.0%) and daily 38 (9.5%).

iii) **Bulletins:-** Here, climatic information were communicated in English language 49 (12.3%) or pidgin 21 (5.3%), local language, 3(0.8%), no response 327 (81.8%). These had very low frequency of supplies where they existed. In terms of frequency, they are published yearly 11 (2.8%), bi annually, 3 (0.8%), monthly 16(4.0), weekly, 13 (3.3%), daily, 18(4.5%), non-response 339 (84.8%)

iv) **Newspapers:-** For newspapers, climate information are communicated in English language 52(13%) Pidgin 13 (3.3%) , local language 17 (4.3%) and no response 318 (79.5%). The frequency of supply of climate information through Newspaper varies as follows. Annually 2 (0.5%), bi annually 18 (4.5%) quarterly 4 (1.0%), monthly 33(8.3%) weekly (18 4.5%), daily, 16(4%) no response 309 (77.3%).

v) **Internet:-** Communicating climate information through the internet varied as follows, English language 45(13%) Pidgin 23 (5.8%) , local language 13 (3.3%) and no response 319 (79.8%). The frequency of supply through the internet varied as follows; quarterly 5 (1.3 %) , bi annually 2 (0.5%) quarterly 5 (1.3 %) , monthly 11(2.8 %) weekly 19 (4.5%), daily, 29 (7.2 %) no response 332 (83%)

vi) **GSM handset:-** Climate information communication through GSM handset were in English language 46 (11.5 %) Pidgin 21 (5.3%) , local language 15 (3.8%) and no response 318 (79.5%) The frequency of supply through GSM handset varied as follows. Daily 28(7.0%), weekly, 24 (6.0%) and non-response is 331 (82.8%).

vii) **Friends as source of climate information:-** Root crop farmers attested that they get readily available information through their friends 69 (17.3%), seldomly,

20 (5%), not available 15 (3.8%) while no response is 30 (75.3%).

This was through various modes. English language 44(11%) Pidgin 24 (6.0%), local language 31 (7.8%) and no response 301 (75.3%). The frequency of supply through friends varied as follows; Daily 27 (6.8%), weekly 19(4.8%) monthly, 14 (3.5%), quarterly 12 (3.0%) bi annually, 9 (2.3%), annually 4 (1.0%) and no response is 314 (78.5%)

viii) **Traditional sources:-** Here climate information were communicated through English language 32(8.0%), Pidgin 30 (7.5 %) , local language 21 (5.3%) and no response 317 (79.3%). The frequency of this supply was Daily 22 (5.5%) weekly 22 (5.5%), monthly 17 (4.4%) and quarterly 1(3%).

ix) **NiMET: -** Climate information from Ni Met were communicated to root crop farmers through English Language 49(12.3), Pidgin 14(3.5%), local language 13 (3.3%) while no response was 324 (81%). The frequency of this supply was Daily 17 (4.3%) weekly 12 (3.0%), monthly 11 (2.8%) and quarterly 7(1.8) bi annually 7(1.8%) annually 4 (1.0 %). non response 342 (85.5%).

AVAILABILITY OF CLIMATE INFORMATION TO ROOT CROP FARMERS ACROSS MEDIA TYPES IN THE STUDY AREA

Table 2: Availability of Climate information across Media Types

Media Type	Readily Available	Seldom Available	Not Available	No Response
Radio	302	26	24	48
Television	66	27	31	276
Bulletin	40	7	42	311
Newspaper	44	30	28	298
Internet	51	12	25	312
GSM Handset	53	17	23	307
Friends	69	20	15	296
Traditional	58	20	17	303
Ni Met	28	23	32	317

Source: Fieldwork 2024.

Table 2 shows the frequency of the availability of climate information to root crop farmers through various media types in the study area.

i) **Radio:** - The study revealed that 302 (75.5%) of root crop farmers had radio as their source of readily available information on climate. Others were, seldomly available 26 (6.5 %), not available 24 (6.0%) no response 48 (12 %).

ii) **Television :** - The use of television as a source of climate information was more discrete as 276 (69%) of root crop farmers had no response while 31(7.8 %) had no access to a television. Climate information was seldomly available to 27(6.8%) while 66 (16.5%) had readily available climate information from television.

iii) **Bulletins :** - The study revealed that 40 (%) of root crop farmers had bulletins as their source of readily available information on climate. Others were, seldomly available 7 (%), not available 42 (%) no response 311 (77.8 %).

iv) **Ni Met:** - Climate information communicated from NiMET was readily available to 28 (7.0%) seldomly available 23(5.8%), not available to 32 (8.0%) of the farmers, while non response were 317 (79.3%).

v) **GSM Handset:-** Root crop farmers attested that they get readily available information through their handsets 53 (13.3%), seldomly, 17(4.3%), not available 23 (5.8%) while no response is 307 (76.8%).

vi) **Newspapers:** - The study revealed that newspapers are not readily available, 28(7.0%). Non response was 298 (74.5%), while 44 (11%) of the farmers stated that they were readily available, and 30 (7.5%) said they were seldomly available.

vii) **Internet :-** Climate information from the internet were readily available, 51 (12.8%). Others, 12(3.0 %) said they were seldomly available, not available 25 (6.3%) and non-response was 312 (78.%).

viii) **Friends:-** Climate information communicated from friends was readily available 69 (17.3%), seldomly available 20 (5.0 %) and not available to 15(3.8%) of root crop farmers.

ix) **Traditional sources:** - Communication on climate to farmers from traditional sources are readily available 58 (14.5%), seldomly available 20 (5.0%), not available 17 (4.3%) while non response was 303 (75%).

Figure 1 clearly shows that the radio is the major source of information to farmers. This corroborates the findings of Myeni (2024) in South Africa. The study also notes that this is followed by the use of other media sources such as mobile phones, friends, television and bulletins. The high percentage of non-responses indicates the high degree of illiteracy of farmers on one hand and poverty on the other. Majority of farmers do not have mobile phones. Consequently, there exists a lack of use of climate information in farmers' decision making in root crop farming. The non-involvement of extension workers is also evident. Rather farmers get climatic information from their friends. This agrees with the findings of Rudzol et al (2020) in the Philippines. In this scenario the farmer is faced with the challenge of adapting his indigenous methods to the prevalent weather variability in their various localities. This is a major challenge to meeting up with the sustainable development goals of forestalling hunger by 2030.

Figure 1: Frequency of supply across Media types

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

BARRIERS TO THE AVAILABILITY AND ACCESS OF CIS TO FARMERS IN THE STUDY AREA

The high degree of illiteracy of farmers depicted by the high percentage of non-responses to the use of the internet, mobile phones and newspapers is a major barrier to farmers access to CIA. Majority of farmers do not have mobile phones, reflecting the level of poverty of the farmers. Institutional challenges also stem from the fact that there is no program of agricultural workers to educate the farmers, or enhance their preparedness to the consequences of climate change on root crop farming. The frequency of the availability of the CIS through the various modes is still very low. What exists is generic rather than being specific to the region. As such, there exists a lack of use of climate information in farmers decision making in root crop farming.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concludes that root crop farmers in the Niger Delta presently lack climate information that will enable them grapple with the on-going climate change phenomenon. A large number of the farmers are poor and illiterate. Some are not able to afford media types such as television or Android phones to access climate information that will help their farm practices. They rely on minimal information that are available to them through the various media types. Monitoring of these farmers by Agricultural extension workers is presently at a very minimal scale (See Table 2). In this vein a lot needs to be done in the agricultural sector in the attempt to attain zero hunger by 2030.

The study recommends the following:

1. Involvement of agricultural extension workers in terms of transmitting climate information to farmers, supervision and monitoring

of root crop farmers in line with weather changing conditions should be reinforced.

2. Extension workers need to be retrained to upscale their knowledge in line with the prevalent weather conditions in their localities.
3. Climate information should be made available to farmers in line with the peculiarities in their agroecological zones. This could be in form seminars and workshops with practical farm demonstration exercises.
4. Government should sponsor more jingles in the local languages so that illiterate farmers can benefit from

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novel climate information that will enable them produce adequate food in the face of climate change occurrence.

In line with Myeni (2024), the study agrees that farmers require more access to internet and mobile applications, awareness campaigns, capacity-building initiatives and co-production of local-specific CIS. This should be accompanied by agrometeorological advisories to overcome these barriers to the access and use of CIS.

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